

Networking the Flight of the Monarchs (performance)

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Example Performance:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Jpbb9dnOHPY&feature=youtu.be>

'Networking the Flight of the Monarchs' (audiovisual telematic performance) - Soundscapes from monarch butterfly reserves in Canada, Mexico and the USA will be live-streamed from open microphones installed by Rob Mackay in 2018 and 2019, and blended with improvised performances networked in real-time from California (David Blink - handpan/trumpet); Mexico (Rolando Rodriguez - poetry); Canada (Jessica Rodriguez - video); and Leeds (Rob Mackay - flutes and computer).

Inspired by Teresa Connors' creative practice, "ecological performativity" enacts a non-anthropocentric model, characterised as the dance of agency between living and non-living systems, human and non-human actors, and the complexity within which they are entangled¹. This model stems from the premise that artistic practice enables different perspectives of the world and becomes an apparatus for change, promoting what we consider "a long overdue ontological shift in the way we exist in the world"².

In this performance, multiple spatialities and temporalities are layered together, creating connections between past, present, and future, as well as multiple webs between human and non-human participants, weaving together in a dance of agency. The intended effect is a kind of 'telephenomenology', building a sense of connectedness, embodied knowing, and empathy.

'Following the Flight of the Monarchs', is an interdisciplinary acoustic ecology project bringing together artists and scientists, connecting with ecosystems and communities along the migration routes of monarch butterflies as they travel the 3,000 mile journey between Mexico and Canada each year.

¹ Connors TM. 2015. Audiovisual installation as ecological performativity. In: Proceedings of the 21st International Symposium on Electronic Art (ISEA2015). Vancouver: ISEA. [Also published as a PhD at The University of Waikato.]

² Welsby C. 2011. Technology, Nature, Software and Networks: Materializing the Post-Romantic Landscape, *Leonardo*, 44:2.

Streamboxes are being installed along the monarch butterfly migration routes between Canada and Mexico. These livestream the soundscapes of these different ecosystems 24/7 via the Locus Sonus Soundmap (<http://locusonus.org/soundmap/051/>). The first of the boxes was successfully installed in the Cerro Pelón UNESCO monarch butterfly reserve in Mexico in 2018. The streams are being used for ecosystem monitoring as well as integrating into artworks which are raising awareness of the issues the monarchs face, whose numbers have declined by nearly 90% over the past two decades.